

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AS A MEANS OF FORMING FUNCTIONAL LITERACY OF SENIOR PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Emotional development of children is one of the most
important areas of professional activity of a teacher.

J. C. Vygotsky

Abstract: in the article the authors talk about the importance of emotional intelligence in the educational process of preschoolers of older age. And the question of their emotional intelligence as a means of forming functional literacy is considered. Detailed descriptions of the influence of emotional intelligence on children's communicative abilities are given.

Key words: emotion, emotional intelligence, games, play abilities, preschooler.

In accordance with the National Educational Standard for Preschool Education, one of the key areas of pedagogical activity is the social and communicative development of children, which is aimed at the acquisition of values and social norms of behaviour, the development of emotional intelligence and interaction with peers and adults, the development of self-regulation and the emotional and volitional sphere.

The component of emotional intelligence of older preschool children includes knowledge of basic human emotional states, the ability to recognise and show them using verbal and non-verbal means of communication, emotional responsiveness, the ability to manage their emotional states in various situations, including in situations of conflict interaction. Also considered as target benchmarks at the end of preschool education are, inter alia, the child's ability to exert will, the ability to follow social norms and rules in various activities, communication and interaction with peers and adults, the ability to rejoice in successes, both his or her own and those of others, empathise with failures, and the ability to adequately express his or her feelings.

At the older preschool age, the child confidently recognises various emotional states, and their spectrum is quite wide and includes both simple, previously mastered emotions (joy, sadness, anger) and complex emotional manifestations (pleasure, admiration, delight, interest, disgust).

Demonstrates their emotional states using verbal and non-verbal means of communication, recognises the emotional states of others, independently determines the causes of various emotional states in themselves, peers and adults, literary heroes.

Knows constructive ways of coping with negative emotional manifestations and is able to manage them; recognises different emotional states in the presented pictures and in various simulated situations, actively suggests constructive ways of resolving conflict situations,

repeats and applies them in everyday interaction with peers under adult supervision and independently.

Here also the main vectors of development of emotional intelligence are the formation of a positive image of 'I' and motivation to study at school, expansion of the range of recognisable emotional states, including negative ones, and socially acceptable ways of their expression, formation of skills of behaviour in conflict situations. Thus, the development of emotional intelligence is an important pedagogical task at the preschool level.

The world is changing, people are changing, and the tasks of education are changing. A modern person should have such skills that help him to organise his own life, to make it effective, interesting, comfortable. That is to have the skills of the XXI century. Consequently, teachers should develop in the younger generation such skills as solving complex problems, critical thinking, creativity, teamwork and people management, recognising their own and others' emotions, analysis and decision-making, negotiation and multitasking. All this will help a person to succeed and develop harmoniously.

There are basic skills that can and should be developed from an early age:

- communication;
- teamwork (or co-operation);
- critical thinking;
- creativity.

In this case, it is noteworthy that it is through the development of basic skills that emotions can be properly developed, and the children's understanding of themselves and the possibilities of their bodies can be shaped.

Emotions, emotional states, and development of the emotional sphere in preschool age are considered by many authors: G. A. Uruntaeva, K. B. Murotmusaev, E. E. Kravtsova, A. V. Zaporozhets, K. Izard, L. S. Vygotsky, S. L. Rubinstein, A. N. Leontyev, and others. For example, E. E. Kravtsova defines emotion as the central mental function of preschool age, noting that a preschooler needs vivid emotional impressions, but at the same time they must learn to manage emotions and be aware of them. G. A. Uruntaeva classifies emotions as a special class of mental processes and states, which constitutes a person's attitude to objects and phenomena of reality, experienced in various forms. A. V. Zaporozhets speaks of anticipatory emotions, considering the emotions themselves as a special form of reflection of reality, with the help of which behavior correction is carried out.

The synthesis of group psychotechnical and role-playing games, as well as creative theater, is of great importance in the system of communicative interaction in developing children's emotional intelligence. This synthesis is not accidental: in a game, as in creativity, the motive for the activity is contained in its process itself, and not in the result. Collective children's creativity creates a special emotional atmosphere that has a beneficial effect on the child's psyche, since in creativity there is always a desire to infect another person with one's feelings.

The work should be carried out according to the following scheme:

1. Assimilation of ideas about non-verbal means of expressing emotions.
2. Developing an understanding of the meaning and significance of various forms of human behavior in emotionally significant situations.
3. Checking and evaluating one's own current behavior based on the knowledge and skills acquired.

The child is given an idea of the emotional atmosphere (partly at the level of intuitive understanding). At the first stage, children learn to "catch" the emotional atmosphere. I explain to the children what an emotional atmosphere is, accompanying the description of the corresponding emotions by listening to musical pieces and showing reproductions of paintings, photographs, and combinations of colors of different emotional coloring. Having felt the difference in emotional experiences, the children gradually begin to turn to their own emotional experience, remembering where and when they experienced similar feelings. This work facilitates the stage of "catch" a certain emotional atmosphere in the process of active embodiment. A musical fragment is given, and the children are asked to perform an improvised dance, to perform some action, the nature of which would correspond to the emotional atmosphere inspired by the music. Some children, when performing this task, completely detach themselves from the outside world, withdraw into themselves in the process of rhythmic movement.

Also, to develop the emotional well-being of children, some scientists have developed psychogymnastics classes, which they recommend using in preschool educational institutions. Psychogymnastics by E. A. Alyabyeva, M. I. Chistyakova is a special class (sketches, games, exercises) aimed at developing and correcting various aspects of the child's psyche (his cognitive and emotional-personal spheres). These meetings are especially necessary for children with excessive fatigue, exhaustion, restlessness, with a hot-tempered or withdrawn character, etc. But it is no less important to play out these sets of exercises with healthy children as a psychophysical release and prevention. You can also include a psychogymnastics complex on days when classes with high intellectual or psychoemotional loads are planned.

The main goal of psychogymnastics meetings is to master the skills of managing one's emotional sphere: to develop in children the ability to understand, be aware of their own and others' emotions, to express them correctly and fully experience them. To do this, the following methodological tasks are set: to focus the child's attention on other people's manifestations of emotions; to imitate other people's emotions; to focus attention on one's own muscular sensations as manifestations of these emotions; to analyze and verbally describe muscular manifestations of emotions; repeated reproduction of emotions in given exercises; control of sensations.

The content of joint activities in psychogymnastics is based on the material of the educational program (work program). Therefore, meetings on psychogymnastics can be held both on the material of the content of one of the types of children's activities: visual, musical, speech, play, etc., and in the integration of several types of children's activities. To organize these forms of work with children, various exercises are offered that contribute to the development of emotions and feelings in children: pantomime riddles, play imitations, play tasks, games.

The structure of organizing this form of work with children includes several stages that contribute to the creation of conditions for the emotional and sensory development of the child. These are the following stages:

Initial stage - (conversation with children, artistic word, riddle, bright colorful toy, surprise moment, etc.); goal: motivating children on the topic of the lesson or other form of work with children.

Stage of experiencing actions - (gymnastics - if it is an active game, morning gymnastics - practicing basic movements or gymnastic exercises); goal: achieving the result of educational, training and developmental tasks.

Stage of organizing emotional communication – goal: training general abilities of verbal and non-verbal influence of children on each other. The content of communication of a child with an adult or a peer includes such exercises as exchanging roles of communication partners, assessing their emotions and the partner's emotions. In such exercises, the child trains to accurately express and experience their feelings, as well as to understand the feelings, emotions, actions, relationships of other children, learns to empathize.

Stage of organizing controlled behavior – goal: training children's ability to regulate their behavioral reactions; methodological tasks: showing and playing out typical situations with psychological difficulties; identifying and recognizing typical forms of adaptive and non-adaptive behavior; acquiring and reinforcing behavioral stereotypes and ways of resolving conflicts that are acceptable to the child; developing skills of independent selection and construction by children of appropriate forms of reactions and actions in different situations. Varying exercises related to children's behavior: playing out situations with typical incidents; responding to children's internal negative experiences that occurred earlier in kindergarten or at home; riddles, for resolving conflict situations; independent fantasy games with the projection of new emotional problems and current proposals; homework to activate positive emotional manifestations, reinforce new forms of emotional response.

The final stage – the goal: to consolidate the content of the proposed material, to consolidate the positive effect that stimulates and organizes the mental and physical activity of children, to balance their emotional state, to improve their well-being and mood. At the end of the lesson, you can use singing and humming along with the teacher, organizing a round dance, approval in the form of hugging each other, etc. For these lessons, it is not recommended to use attributes for children, as it distracts them from performing the main tasks of joint activities.

Introduction to fundamental emotions should be carried out both during the entire educational process and at special joint meetings, where children experience emotional states, verbalize their experiences, get acquainted with the experience of their peers, as well as with literature, painting, and music. In this way, their range of conscious emotions expands, they begin to understand themselves and others more deeply, and empathy towards adults and children arises more often. With the help of role-playing games, outdoor games, game exercises, elements of psychogymnastics, expressive movement techniques, etudes, psychomuscular training, facial expressions and pantomime, literary works and fairy tales (dramatization games), the child's emotional sphere is developed, and, consequently, the emotional intelligence of children.

It should be especially noted that integration with the family is significant for both parties, as it has a positive effect not only on the child's development process, but also on changing the characteristics of communication between parents and their children. Consequently, the inclusion of parents in the educational process, as well as the development of certain aspects related to emotional disorders in preschoolers, can be considered further promising steps in implementing the tasks of forming the emotional sphere as the basis for the development of communicative competence in older preschool children.

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